

OPENING

1. How do training programs usually take place in your company?
 2. What usually makes you decide to participate in a corporate training program?
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TRAINING

1. How does the training format influence your decision to participate in a corporate training program?
 2. How does the total training workload (number of hours) influence your decision to participate in a corporate training program?
 3. How does the training content influence your decision to participate in a corporate training program?
 4. How does the instructional method of the training influence your decision to participate in a corporate training program?
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ORGANIZATION

1. How does leadership encourage you to participate in corporate training programs?
 2. How do mandatory training programs influence your decision to participate in corporate training?
 3. How does your workload influence your decision to participate in corporate training programs?
 4. How are corporate training programs related to career advancement or promotion?
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INDIVIDUAL ASPECTS

1. How do you usually choose which corporate training programs to participate in?

2. How do you perceive the relationship between corporate training programs and your professional goals?
 3. How does a challenging training program influence your decision to participate in corporate training?
 4. How are corporate training programs related to career advancement or promotion?
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CLOSING

1. Is there anything important about these training programs that has not yet been mentioned?